

On the applicability of low-cost GNSS antennas to precise surveying applications

Karol Dawidowicz* , Katarzyna StępniaK and Grzegorz Krzan

University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Oczapowskiego 1 10-719 Olsztyn, Poland

E-mail: karol.dawidowicz@uwm.edu.pl

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Abstract

This study addresses the scientific question of the applicability of low-cost antennas to the most precise Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) applications. First of all, we inspect the implications of the availability and quality of low-cost antenna PCC models for precise positioning. From this point of view, we analyze the selected performance indicators of multi-constellation positioning with the representative set of low-cost mass-market GNSS receiver antennas. The processing strategy was based on the relative positioning model, considered the most reliable and precise one. To isolate the antenna-related errors from atmospheric propagation ones, we conducted an experiment based on an ultra-short baseline. As the main indications of low-cost antenna performance, we considered distance and height residuals, defined as the difference between benchmarks and the retrieved from GNSS measurements. We found that the low-cost antenna's phase center variation effect may significantly affect the final results. On the other hand, the results obtained using certain configurations of low-cost antennas were characterized by only slightly higher standard deviations and discrepancies with respect to benchmark values than those obtained with surveying or geodetic equipment. We identify several sets of low-cost antennas where distance residuals do not exceed 4 mm and height residuals do not exceed 6 mm, which shows the low-cost antenna performance comparable to those achieved using high-grade antennas. On this basis, we conclude that selected low-cost antennas can meet the requirements of high-precision surveying applications.

Keywords: low-cost antennas, GNSS, surveying, positioning

1. Introduction

In recent years, the development of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) has not only focused on satellite constellations by introducing new signals and services.

Another direction in developing the GNSS market is its popularization by creating more affordable devices acquiring satellite signals, such as smartphones, wearable watches, or other mass-market GNSS chipsets (Paziewski 2020, Zangenehjad and Gao 2021, Bahadur and Schön 2024). So far, low-cost GNSS receivers have been analyzed and tested for various applications. The assessments of low-cost receiver observation noise suggested that such observations may even address the requirements of the most demanding and precise applications. In this regard, we identify surveying, deformation, and vibration monitoring as one of the most challenging (Cina and Piras 2015, Caldera *et al* 2016, Hamza *et al* 2021).

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

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These tests were often performed in a relative mode over short baselines under favorable surveying conditions (Xue *et al* 2021, 2023, Paziewski *et al* 2024). Some experiments were also made in challenging conditions and over long baselines but the obtained results showed a visible decrease in performance (Biagi *et al* 2016). In some studies, geodetic GNSS hardware was used as a benchmark to test low-cost ones in different scenarios. The results of these tests indicated that, in some cases, low-cost receivers can have performance comparable to geodetic ones (Tsakiri *et al* 2017, Stepniak and Paziewski 2022). Geodetic, as well as single-frequency (SF) low-cost GNSS receivers, were tested in Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) mode following the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standard 17 123-8 (Garrido-Carretero *et al* 2019). The uncertainties for the geodetic instruments were found at the level of 2.5 mm for the horizontal and 4.5 mm for the vertical components. For low-cost receivers, the corresponding values were 5.5 mm and 11.0 mm, respectively. However, it should be noted that over short baselines, low-cost receivers' performance was comparable to geodetic ones. In (De Ponte Müller *et al* 2013), low-cost u-blox LEA 4 T receivers were assessed in a controlled error-free environment in static and dynamic scenarios. The authors focused on multipath and showed that its level was much smaller in a static scenario. They also proved that in the case of a kinematic scenario, the multipath may severely degrade the performance. Guo *et al* (2017) reported that SF low-cost receivers provided low noise in open sky conditions, and their performance was comparable to that of geodetic receivers over short baselines.

The above analyses were focused mainly on GPS-only data, whereas recently, low-cost multi-frequency multi-constellation GNSS receivers and antennas were released on the market. Only a few papers deal with multi-frequency, low-cost GNSS receivers tracking signals from all available constellations. For example, Nie *et al* (2020) proposed a new method that incorporates both single and dual-frequency (DF) measurements as well as precise ionospheric products. In this approach, DF ionospheric-free code and phase combinations, as well as SF ionosphere-corrected code measurements, are applied for position determination. The method was tested using the low-cost u-blox ZED-F9P receiver. The results showed that the proposed method reached a horizontal accuracy of half a meter in real-time precise point positioning mode faster. Also, a DF u-blox ZED-F9P receiver, combined with a u-blox ANN-MB patch antenna, was tested in short and long-baseline RTK modes (Odolinski and Teunissen 2020). In long baselines, it had worse performance than the geodetic GNSS instruments. Multi-frequency low-cost GNSS receivers and antennas were also validated against geodetic ones in the study of Semler *et al* (2019), Hamza *et al* (2020) and Krietemeyer *et al* (2020).

The quality of receiver antennas has a meaningful impact on GNSS positioning performance (Dawidowicz 2011). In this regard, one of the key issues is knowing the exact position of the antenna phase center (APC). As it is well known, changes in the position of the antenna's phase center can be as large as several centimeters. Consequently, neglecting APC

can lead to meaningful errors not only in the vertical coordinate component but also in the horizontal ones. Currently, there are only a few centers conducting GNSS antenna calibrations (Dawidowicz *et al* 2021, Kröger *et al* 2021, Tupek *et al* 2023). Due to the high demand, the waiting time for calibration is long, and the service is expensive, which explains the common lack of phase center corrections (PCC) models for low-cost antennas. Other issues are the low repeatability of the PCC within a particular antenna model and other antenna-related factors, such as susceptibility to the multipath effect (Paziewski 2022). Consequently, the low phase center stability, usually lacking PCC models, and vulnerability to multipath effect results in constraining the application of low-cost antennas to precise solutions (Krzan *et al* 2020, Dawidowicz *et al* 2023). However, few low-cost antennas with PCC models are on the market, which motivated us to examine whether they can offer performance comparable to high-grade antennas and thus address the requirements of the most precise applications. Specifically, we inspect the implications of the availability and quality of low-cost antenna PCC models for precise positioning which was not done before. We verify the research hypothesis on the usability of such consumer-grade antennas supported with PCC models for precise surveying applications. In the following section, we present the data collection, the experiment design, and the methods used for the antenna performance validation. In this section, we also inspect the PCC models of the antennas employed. Next we compare satellite signal tracking performance for different types of low-cost antennas. In the subsequent section, we turn to the core of the research, which is the validation of the antennas' performance in the positioning domain. Here, we inspect the ambiguity resolution and geometry domains by analyzing the impact of low-cost antennas on selected positioning performance parameters. Finally, we summarize the results and provide the conclusion in the last section.

2. Experiment design and methods

Below, we present the data collection and the experiment design. Next, the methods used for the antenna performance validation are described.

2.1. Experiment design

A setup consisting of three types of low-cost antennas that support GPS, Galileo, GLONASS, and BeiDou systems measurements, and gain > 25 dB were selected for analysis. Specifically, we employed ELT0149, u-blox ANN-MB-00, and Tallysman TWI7972 + GP NONE low-cost antennas (Dawidowicz *et al* 2024). The first one is deprived of any PCC. For the second one, only the vertical component of the phase center offset (PCO) for GPS signals is provided. The last one, in turn, is characterized by a PCO and zenith-angle-only phase center variation (PCV). In addition, two surveying and geodetic grades Trimble antennas, namely TRM105000.10 and TRM159900.00, provide benchmark performance results (figure 1, table 1).

Figure 1. GNSS antennas used in the experiment. From the left, three low-cost and two surveying and geodetic grade antennas are presented: ELT0149, TWI7972 + GP NONE, u-blox ANN-MB-00, TRM105000.10 NONE, and TRM159900.00 NONE.

Table 1. GNSS antennas used in the experiment.

GNSS Antenna	Serial Number	PCC model
TRM159900.00 NONE	6126333759	igs14_2196.atx
TRM105000.10 NONE #1	3121102632	igs14_2196.atx
TRM105000.10 NONE #2	61053R0021	igs14_2196.atx
u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	AGA556022-S0-A24	manufacturer PCO
u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	AGA556022-S0-A9	manufacturer PCO
TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	20210910	PCO and zenith-angle PCV
TWI7972 + GP NONE #2	20210630	PCO and zenith-angle PCV
ELT0149	—	none

In the assessment, the ultra-short baseline measurement system, mounted on the roof and providing a fully open sky view, was employed. A steel rod with a pair of antenna mounting points was used as a fixed ultra-short baseline (figure 2). The distance between the antenna mounting points (l_b) equaled to 1601.0 mm. The distance of the base was determined with an accuracy of 0.5 mm. The mechanism for leveling was also used in order to provide precisely the same heights at both ends of the test base ($dh_b = 0.0$ mm). The motivation for implementing this kind of measurement system was the need to isolate antenna effects from other errors. In other words, we aimed to exclude the impact of errors such as multipath and ionosphere or troposphere refraction, as they can be considered the same at both ends of the ultra-short baseline and, therefore, are eliminated in double-differencing. Another benefit of using such a system is the ability to measure the length of the baseline connecting the antenna mounting points precisely. The baseline components, such as known length and height difference, will serve as benchmark values for GNSS solutions.

The session duration at both mounting points and each measuring day was 16 h, from 8:00:00–24:00:00 UTC. An interval of 5 s and an elevation mask of 0° were adopted. The motivation for using a 0° elevation mask was to precisely evaluate differences in data recording capacities of the antennas used in the experiments.

According to table 2, five versions of antenna pairs' configurations were adopted:

- homogenous antennas at both ends of the baseline,
 - A) surveying antennas (set #1),
 - B) low-cost antennas (sets #2, 3),

Figure 2. Ultra short-baseline measurement system with two antenna mounting points: P1 (left) and P2 (right).

- nonhomogenous (mixed type) antennas: low-cost, surveying, or geodetic at both ends of the baseline,
 - C) geodetic and surveying antennas (set #4),
 - D) low-cost and geodetic antennas (sets #5, 6, 7),
 - E) low-cost and low-cost antennas (sets #8, 9, 10).

The adopted configurations made it possible to analyze the quality of the GNSS solution when the baseline is formed using antennas of the same type (Configurations A and B) or when different types of antennas are combined in the network (Configurations C, D, and E). In Configurations A and C, there are sets with surveying/geodetic-grade antennas (19 March

Table 2. Data collection timetable.

Conf.	# of antenna set	Date	DOY	Antenna	
				Mounting point P1	Mounting point P2
A	1	19 March 2022	78	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM105000.10 NONE #2
B	2	29 March 2022	88	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TWI7972 + GP NONE #2
	3	18 March 2022	77	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2
C	4	23 March 2022	82	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE
D	5	28 March 2022	87	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE
	6	21 March 2022	80	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	TRM159900.00 NONE
	7	22 March 2022	81	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	TRM159900.00 NONE
E	8	30 March 2022	89	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2
	9	27 March 2022	86	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	ELT0149
	10	20 March 2022	79	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	ELT0149

2022 and 23 March 2022). The outcomes of these measurements will serve as a benchmark for the results obtained with low-cost antennas.

2.2. Data processing and validation methods

The processing was performed using three processing strategies, namely GPS-only, Galileo-only, and GPS + GLONASS + Galileo solution. In the processing, we used the PCC models included in `igs14_2196.atx` file and valid at the time of the data collection, as well as the available information on PCC models for low-cost antennas provided by the manufacturers. In the case of GPS observations, PCC information was available for surveying and geodetic antennas, as well as for TWI7972 + GP NONE low-cost antenna. For Galileo signals, PCC corrections that are valid for GPS constellations were adopted. Finally, by adopting the GPS + GLONASS + Galileo solution, we aimed to analyze the performance and identify the possible constraints of low-cost antennas in precise multi-GNSS positioning. The processing of GNSS observations was performed in a two-hour session length regime. This made it possible to check the solution's repeatability for medium-length sessions. This means that data were collected during a part of the full satellite's revolution period which can reveal additional influences of changes in the position of the antenna's phase center on the final results. On the other hand, Kazmierski *et al* (2023) proved that a two-hour session is sufficient to achieve stable and precise results in double-differenced (DD) GNSS processing carried out on short baselines.

The GNSS observations were processed using the Bernese GNSS Software v.5.2. The solution was performed in a relative mode, i.e. based on the DF DD GNSS observations. The SIGMA method was applied for ambiguity resolution of the DF DD phase observations. GNSS data with a minimum elevation angle of 3° above the horizon and an elevation-dependent weighting scheme were used. All processing parameters were applied following the guidelines of the EPN Analysis Centers

Table 3. GNSS data processing parameters.

Parameter	Setting
Constellations	GPS, GLONASS, Galileo
Observations	Dual frequency double-differenced code and phase observations
Positioning model	Relative
The elevation cut-off angle	3°
Source of orbits, clocks, Earth orientation parameters	CODE MGEX, final products
Antenna phase center position and variation model	Type-mean <code>igs14_2196.atx</code> , provided by Tallysman manufacturer for TWI7972 + GP NONE, none for ELT0149 and u-blox ANN-MB-00
Ocean tide model	FES2004
Global model of the ionosphere	CODE, final products
Troposphere modeling	Global Pressure and Temperature (GPT) and Global Mapping Function (GMF)
Horizontal tropospheric gradient model	Chen and Herring (1997)
Conditions imposed on tropospheric parameter estimates	Fixed to the values from the model

(EPN 2023) and in accordance with the recommendations for Bernese software (Dach *et al* 2015). Detailed parameters of the processing strategy can be found in table 3. From this step's results, we adopted ambiguity resolution success rate (ARSR) as the first indicator of the positioning performance with selected antennas.

The primary outcomes from GNSS data processing were Earth-centered Earth fixed coordinates. On their basis, we have computed the distances in three-dimensional (3D) space and height differences between the points of the ultra-short baseline. The solution performance assessment was done

through a comparison of the 3D distances and elevation components with their known benchmark values. We inspected the 3D distances (l), which is one of the basic measurements in surveying and the ellipsoidal height differences (dh), which allowed us to analyze the potential usability of low-cost antennas for GNSS height differences determination. Due to the fact that the impact of changes in the position of the antenna's phase center and possible deficiencies in its modeling are revealed mainly in the vertical component of the position, the latter analyses are particularly relevant.

The distance obtained from GNSS measurements is determined using a well-known formula:

$$l = \sqrt{(X_A - X_B)^2 + (Y_A - Y_B)^2 + (Z_A - Z_B)^2}. \quad (1)$$

Where subscripts A and B refer to the antenna mounting points on the left and right arm of the test base and $\{X, Y, Z\}$ denotes a set of geocentric Cartesian coordinates of one of the points, A or B at the ends of the ultra-short baseline.

Accordingly, the GNSS-derived height differences (dh_s) are determined as:

$$dh_s = h_B - h_A, \quad (2)$$

where h is the ellipsoidal height of the point obtained from the GNSS solution. Finally, we define distance and elevation residuals (Δl , Δh) as the difference between the benchmark (b) and the retrieved from the GNSS solution (s) values:

$$\Delta l = l_b - l_s, \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta h = dh_b - dh_s. \quad (4)$$

2.3. Characteristics of PCC models of employed low-cost antennas

Here, we inspect the PCC models of the employed antennas. As for the low-cost antennas, there is no full PCC model available, i.e. no azimuthal dependency is available.

For the ELT0149 antenna, there is no information on the position of the phase center, so both PCO and PCV adopted in processing were equal to zero. For the u-blox ANN-MB-00 antenna, only the vertical component of the PCO for GPS signals is available. For the TWI7972 + GP NONE antenna, more complete phase center position information is available. This includes PCO value for GPS signals and corrections for PCV. However, these corrections are derived from relative calibration and have been subsequently converted to values compatible with absolute. Additionally, the corrections available for GPS-only frequencies are given as a function of the zenith-angle-only.

Full phase center position data are provided for surveying (TRM105000.10 NONE) and geodetic (TRM159900.00 NONE) grade antennas, which are derived from an absolute out-door calibration. In the study, we used a type-mean correction model, which is an averaging of PCC values derived from multiple individual calibrations of several antennas of

the same type. Finally, it should be recalled that in the case of Galileo signals PCC corrections were adopted for GPS ones.

3. Satellite tracking performance

We compare satellite signal tracking performance for different types of low-cost antennas. In this regard, we analyze a number of recorded observations and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

3.1. Number of observations

Firstly, we used the percentage difference formula to compare the total number of observations recorded by tested antennas connected to two high-grade Trimble alloy receivers in identical measurement configurations (table 4).

The number of tracked satellite vehicles (SVs) on subsequent measurement days can be assumed to be identical. Also, the measurement conditions on the two antennas mounted on an ultra-short baseline can be considered the same. For these reasons, the differences in the number of collected observations will refer to the capability of the tested antennas to track GNSS signals. For simplicity, we present only the carrier phase observations volume, as corresponding statistics for code observations were very similar.

First of all, we check if measurement conditions at both ends of the baselines can be considered the same. For this purpose, we analyze the results for antenna sets #1, 2, and 3 (table 4), when the same type of antenna was mounted at the test base ends. The number of observations is similar for low-cost u-blox ANN-MB-00 and TWI7972 + GP NONE antenna pairs. For the u-blox ANN-MB-00 antenna, generally, slightly more observations were collected by the antenna located on mounting point P2, but the differences do not exceed 2%. In the case of the TWI7972 + GP NONE, antenna set #2, more observations were collected on mounting point P1, especially for the Galileo system. In the case of the surveying TRM105000.10 NONE antenna pair, the difference was revealed only for GLONASS data and reached 1%. These results show that the measurement conditions at both points can be considered the same.

In the next step, we analyze results for configurations C, D, and E with mixed-type antennas. The most prominent differences were comparing mixed antennas when one is TRM159900.00 NONE. In the case of antenna set #5, E1 Galileo frequency, differences in the number of recorded observations reach up to 14%. The reason may be related to the multipath effect protection rings in the TRM159900.00 NONE antennas. In the case of mixed low-cost antennas, the maximum difference in recorded observations reaches up to 6% (antenna set #10, L1 for GLONASS and antenna set #9, L5 for Galileo). In both cases, more observations were recorded on mounting point P1. Finally, the difference in recorded observations is much smaller for the antenna set #8 and does not exceed 2%.

Table 4. Differences in the number of recorded carrier phase observations between antennas for GPS, GLONASS, and Galileo signals. Positive values indicate that more observations were recorded on mounting point P1.

# of antenna set	The antenna on the mounting point P1	The antenna on the mounting point P2	GPS		GLONASS		Galileo	
			L1 [%]	L2 [%]	L1 [%]	L2 [%]	E1 [%]	E5a [%]
1	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM105000.10 NONE #2	0	0	-1	-1	0	0
2	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TWI7972 + GP NONE #2	0	0	-1	1	2	2
3	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	-1	-1	-2	-1	2	-2
4	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	2	2	7	6	11	10
5	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	2	2	5	4	14	11
6	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	TRM159900.00 NONE	2	1	4	2	13	11
7	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	2	0	4	0	11	8
8	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	0	1	0	1	2	2
9	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	ELT0149	0	1	1	2	2	6
10	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	ELT0149	-1	-1	6	4	0	4

Table 5. Differences in the SNR of carrier phase observations between antennas for GPS, GLONASS, and Galileo signals. Positive values indicate that higher SNR rates were recorded by an antenna at mounting point P1 with respect to the one at P2.

# of antenna set	The antenna on the mounting point P1	The antenna on the mounting point P2	GPS		GLONASS		Galileo	
			L1 [%]	L2 [%]	L1 [%]	L2 [%]	E1 [%]	E5a [%]
1	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM105000.10 NONE #2	-1.6	-0.8	-2.4	-0.6	-1.5	-0.8
2	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TWI7972 + GP NONE #2	0.4	0.3	0.2	1.0	0.4	-0.2
3	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	-0.3	-0.4	-0.2	0.7	-0.2	-2.5
4	TRM105000.10 NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	1.7	1.5	0.7	-0.6	0.5	-1.5
5	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	2.0	-0.5	-0.2	-10.1	0.1	-15.5
6	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	TRM159900.00 NONE	2.6	-2.3	3.3	-13.3	0.8	-16.2
7	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #1	TRM159900.00 NONE	2.7	-3.5	2.0	-14.6	1.1	-19.7
8	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	-0.7	1.8	-3.8	4.3	-0.7	1.2
9	TWI7972 + GP NONE #1	ELT0149	-0.8	1.7	-3.1	-1.9	-0.3	2.3
10	u-blox ANN-MB-00 #2	ELT0149	2.3	-1.5	10.0	-8.5	4.1	3.1

3.2. SNR analysis

The parameter further analyzed was the value of the SNR. Since the measurement conditions on the two antennas mounted at the ultra-short base can be considered identical, the differences in the SNR highlight the differences in tracking performance between antennas.

Antenna sets #1, 2, and 3 in table 5 present the mean SNR values at two mounting points when the same type of antenna was used during measurements. The SNR obtained for data recorded by both antennas is comparable in all three cases: the differences do not exceed 2.5%. This was expected, considering the ultra-short distance between the two antenna mounting points. These results demonstrate that any differences detected in the mixed-type antenna configurations arise from different recording capacities used in measurement antennas.

Analyzing mixed-type antenna results, it is visible that the SNR differences reach higher values, exceeding 2.5%. The only exception is antenna set #4, where two high-grade antennas were used. Comparing pairs when low-cost antennas were mixed with geodetic ones, i.e. antenna sets #5, 6, and 7, it is seen that GPS SNR values for L1 and L2 frequencies are also comparable. The higher difference, reaching 3.5%, was obtained for GPS L2 frequency for u-blox ANN-MB-00 and TRM159900.00 NONE in antenna set #7. In the case of GLONASS and Galileo signals, differences in SNR are

much more pronounced. The highest values, as expected, were obtained for the TRM159900.00 NONE antenna. Depending on the antenna set, differences in SNR achieve values from 10.1% to 19.7%. Example results of SNR for this configuration are presented in figure 3. From the figure we can read that there are noticeable differences in SNR recorded at the same time at both antenna mounting points. This is especially true for L2 and E5a frequencies. As expected, a higher SNR was registered at the mounting point where the TRM159900.00 NONE high-grade antenna was mounted.

4. The results of antenna validation in the positioning domain

Now, we turn to the core of the research, which is the validation of the antennas' performance in the positioning domain. In this regard, we inspect the ambiguity resolution and geometry domains by analyzing the impact of the low-cost antennas on selected positioning performance parameters.

4.1. Ambiguity resolution domain

In figures 4–6, we present the ARSR for all processing scenarios: GPS-only, Galileo-only, and GPS + Galileo + GLONASS, respectively. Analyzing the

Figure 3. Comparison of SNR values for GPS SV 29, GLONASS SV 21, and Galileo SV 13 on DOY 80.

Figure 4. The ambiguity resolution success rates for GPS-only solution.

results presented in figure 4, it can be concluded that the ambiguity resolution performed the best when the antennas of the same type were used. In the case of set #1 with two surveying antennas TRM105000.10 NONE, the ambiguity success rate reached 100%. For two cases with low-cost antennas, i.e. antenna set #3 with u-blox ANN-MB-00 and antenna set #2 with TWI7972 + GP NONE, the mean ARSR were slightly lower but still very high and equaled 98.8% and 99.3%, respectively, which confirms the comparable performance of such antenna pair to the one with high-grade antennas. On the other hand, the lowest success rate was obtained when mixed low-cost antennas were mounted on the test base, i.e. antenna sets #8, 9, and 10.

In the case of the Galileo-only solution given in figure 5, the ambiguity success rates were noticeably lower in comparison to the GPS-only solution. The mean ARSR values varied from 75.4% in the case of antenna set #5, to 90.6% for

antenna set #10. We attribute such an effect to the noticeably fewer tracked Galileo satellites than GPS. On average, during the test measurements, the number of observed Galileo satellites was 6, while the number of GPS satellites reached 11. In two extreme cases, the ARSR dropped below 50%, i.e. session 4 for antenna pair TWI7972 + GP NONE/TRM159900.00 NONE and session 3 for antenna pair TRM105000.10 NONE/TRM159900.00 NONE, which caused so-called *float* solution. As a consequence, these results were not included in analyses. What also should be highlighted is that we did not find a correlation between the type of antennas mounted on the test base and the ARSR.

Finally, for multi-GNSS solutions, the highest ARSR equaled 100%, was obtained when two surveying antennas TRM105000.10 NONE were mounted on the test baseline (figure 6). For two low-cost homogenous antenna sets, i.e. Configuration B, ARSR was also very high and did not

Figure 5. The ambiguity resolution success rates for Galileo-only solution.

Figure 6. The ambiguity resolution success rates for GPS + Galileo + GLONASS solution.

fall, on average, below 97.9 %. On the other hand, the two lowest ARSR statistics were present when mixed low-cost antennas were mounted on the test base, i.e. antenna sets #8 and 9, which is in line with the results of the GPS-only solution and confirms the elimination of the receiver antenna PCO + PCV when the same antennas are used in the ultra-short baseline.

4.2. Geometry domain

We investigate the distance and the height difference residual indicators, which were defined when validation methods were introduced. We recall that such residuals are computed as the difference between the benchmark and the retrieved from the GNSS solution values (equations (3) and (4)). Figure 7 presents the example results in the geometry domain for the nonhomogenous antenna pair in set #6, namely u-blox ANN-MB-00 and TRM159900.00 NONE. The complete results of this analysis are shown in figures 8–10, where maximum and minimum residual, mean residual, and standard deviation (SD)

were presented, and in tables 6 and 7, with mean residual and SD.

As seen in figure 7, the most stable results were obtained for GPS-only and multi-GNSS solutions. The differences between GNSS-derived and the reference values are the most prominent for the Galileo-only solution. The higher scattering of residuals also characterizes this case. On the other hand, in all solutions, there is some systematic bias to reference values for both distance and elevation components, which is most likely due to deficiencies in the PCC model of the u-blox ANN-MB-00 low-cost antenna.

In the case of GPS-only solutions, when the same types of antennas are used (Configurations A and B), the lowest height and distance residuals were obtained for a pair with TRM105000.10 NONE surveying antennas (figure 8), as expected. These results are also characterized by the lowest SD value, which equals 2.7 mm for distance (Δl) and 3.6 mm for height difference (Δh). For two low-cost homogenous antenna sets, i.e. Configuration B, the results obtained are only slightly

Figure 7. Distance (Δl) and height difference (Δh) residuals for 2 h-long session solutions for the u-blox ANN-MB-00 and TRM159900.00 NONE antenna pair (set #6).

Figure 8. Distance and height difference residuals computed with respect to the benchmark values for 2 h-long session GPS-only solutions. In red, we marked the results for Configuration A, the pink color refers to Configuration B, blue indicates the results obtained for Configuration C, and finally, light and dark green colors correspond to Configurations D and E, respectively.

Figure 9. Distance and height difference residuals computed with respect to the benchmark values for 2 h-long session Galileo-only solutions. The configurations are distinguished by different colors (cf figure 8).

Figure 10. Distance and height difference residuals computed with respect to the benchmark values for 2 h-long session multi-GNSS solutions. The configurations are distinguished by different colors (cf figure 8).

worse. Although mean Δl and Δh SD reach a little higher values, Δl SD is comparable, and in the case of antenna set #3, mean Δh was lower than in Configuration A. The worst results were obtained in the last group, where only nonhomogenous low-cost antennas were used, which also could be anticipated. High values of mean residuals and the highest values of SD characterized these solutions. For set #8 with TWI7972 + GP NONE and u-blox ANN-MB-00 antennas, the higher values of SD, which equal 5.6 mm and 18.9 mm for distance and height difference components, respectively, were noticed. Finally, in Configuration D with nonhomogenous low-cost and geodetic antennas, the smallest SDs equaled 1.2 mm for Δl and 1.4 mm for Δh were obtained for set #4. Such results agree well with the ambiguity resolution domain and prove the noticeable elimination of the receiver antenna-related errors when homogenous antennas are used in the baseline solution.

In the case of the Galileo-only solution, for the same types of antennas in pair, the lowest residuals, again, were obtained for the solution with two TRM105000.10 NONE surveying antennas (-1.8 mm for Δl and -0.1 mm for Δh). This solution also has the smallest SD value of 4.0 mm for Δl and 6.2 mm for Δh . Comparing these results to Configuration B, where homogenous low-cost antennas were used, it can be seen that the results are quite comparable. This is especially true for mean Δl and Δh . In the case of SD slightly lower values characterize results obtained with surveying antennas. In Configuration E with mixed low-cost antennas, the worst results were obtained in set #8 with the TWI7972 + GP NONE and u-blox ANN-MB-00 antenna pair. In this case, we achieved high systematic shifts equal to -14.2 mm for Δl and 24.1 mm for Δh , and the highest SD values equal to 35.7 mm for Δl and 21.8 mm for Δh . Finally, the best results in Configuration D were obtained for set #4 with TRM105000.10 NONE and TRM159900.00 NONE high-grade antenna pair. It should be noted that, in general, mean Δl and Δh in Configuration D are reaching very similar values to those of Configuration C where surveying and geodetic antennas

were involved. What is also worth noticing is that the results obtained in the Galileo-only solution are generally characterized by higher discrepancies with respect to the benchmark values and higher SDs than those obtained in the GPS-only solution. This could be attributed to the noticeably lower number of tracked Galileo satellites than GPS ones and, consequently, to a lower ambiguity success rate.

In the multi-GNSS solution for configuration with the same types of antennas used, the best results were obtained for a pair with two surveying TRM105000.10 NONE antenna with mean residuals equal -0.8 mm for Δl and 2.1 mm for Δh . Worse, but still high-performance results, with mean residuals equal to 6.8 mm for Δl and 2.4 mm for Δh , were obtained for set #3 with two low-cost u-blox ANN-MB-00 antennas. The highest mean residuals for Δh , equaled -14.4 mm, were obtained for the low-cost TWI7972 + GP NONE antenna pair. In Configuration E with nonhomogenous low-cost antennas, the highest SDs were obtained for the TWI7972 + GP NONE and u-blox ANN-MB-00 antenna pair. In the remaining non-homogenous configuration, the lowest SD was obtained for the pair with surveying and geodetic antenna, equaling 0.4 mm and 2.3 mm for distance and height components, respectively. The mean distance residual was also the lowest for this antenna pair, equaling 1.9 mm.

What transpires from table 6 is that the most stable results in the distance domain were achieved in the case of multi-GNSS and GPS-only solutions. The smallest SD values in all antenna sets characterize these two variants. We attribute the lower accuracy of Galileo solutions to a low number of tracked Galileo satellites and, consequently, to poorer ambiguity resolution performance. Analyzing mean distance residuals' values, it can be seen that the most precise results in solutions where low-cost antennas were involved were achieved in Configuration B with the same types of antennas in the baseline or, alternatively, using the low-cost antennas paired with geodetic ones (Configuration D).

In order to focus on the best solutions, we have proposed to select those cases where SD is below 3 mm and, at the

Table 6. Mean distance residuals (Δl) and standard deviation (SD) obtained from 2-hour-long session solutions.

Antenna configuration	# of antenna set	Mean Δl (mm)			SD (mm)		
		G	E	GRE	G	E	GRE
A	1	0.0	-1.8	-0.8	2.7	4.0	2.1
B	2	5.2	2.3	4.0	2.8	7.4	1.6
	3	6.4	8.4	6.8	3.0	10.5	1.6
C	4	3.2	-0.9	1.9	1.2	2.2	0.4
D	5	-5.2	5.0	-2.4	2.7	9.8	2.3
	6	-5.8	-7.8	-5.1	1.1	8.5	1.6
	7	3.6	0.7	2.0	2.6	5.1	1.6
E	8	10.5	-14.2	6.1	5.6	35.7	3.5
	9	5.2	2.3	4.2	2.1	7.4	1.6
	10	-14.3	-14.3	-13.3	4.0	14.6	1.4

same time, the mean distance residual does not exceed 4 mm. In configurations with homogenous antennas, antenna set #1 in GPS-only and multi-GNSS solutions, as well as antenna set #2 in multi-GNSS solution, meet these requirements. As expected, the best results were obtained when two identical TRM105000.10 NONE surveying antennas were used. Also, using two TWI7972 + GP NONE low-cost antennas in a multi-GNSS approach allows the distance to be measured with the required accuracy. In other words, low-cost antennas may yield positioning performance comparable to geodetic ones, providing that homogenous antennas are used in the relative solution.

In Configurations C and D, on the other hand, antenna set #4 in all three solution variants, antenna set #7 in GPS-only and multi-constellation solutions as well as antenna set #5 in multi-constellation solution meet the adopted requirements. The application of low-cost antennas paired with geodetic ones also may provide competitive to geodetic antennas' results. As expected, the poorest results were obtained for Configuration E with nonhomogenous low-cost antennas. The main reason, in our opinion, could be deficiencies in the PCV modeling for low-cost antennas.

The results presented in table 7, show that the most stable results in height domain were achieved in multi-GNSS and possibly in the GPS-only solutions. Analyzing mean height residuals values, it can be seen that the most precise results were achieved, generally, in the case of solution with the homogenous types of antennas in the baseline (Configurations A and B).

To expose the best solutions in terms of height domain, we have selected the cases where SD is below 5 mm and, at the same time, mean height residuals do not exceed 6 mm. The adoption of such values was motivated by the fact that the vertical component of the GNSS position is typically characterized by an error 1.7 times higher than the horizontal coordinates. In the first two Configurations (A, B), antenna set #1 in GPS-only and multi-constellation solutions and set #2 in multi-constellation solutions meet these requirements. Again, as expected, the best results were obtained when two identical

Table 7. Mean height difference residuals (Δh) and standard deviation (SD) obtained from 2-hour-long session solutions.

Antenna configuration	# of antenna set	Mean Δh (mm)			SD (mm)		
		G	E	GRE	G	E	GRE
A	1	2.7	-0.1	2.1	3.6	6.2	2.8
B	2	-18.0	-2.4	-14.4	6.3	15.6	2.4
	3	0.8	3.9	2.4	8.3	10.4	5.0
C	4	11.5	11.2	12.5	1.4	4.0	2.3
D	5	-13.2	-8.6	-11.8	2.3	14.4	4.0
	6	-11.0	-1.6	-10.6	4.9	9.1	3.6
	7	-5.8	-10.6	-10.9	6.4	13.4	3.4
E	8	5.7	24.1	5.8	18.9	21.8	9.3
	9	-18.0	-2.4	-14.4	6.3	15.6	2.4
	10	-5.9	1.1	-5.5	5.5	14.3	3.0

TRM105000.10 NONE surveying antennas were used. But what is worth highlighting is that also using two homogenous u-blox ANN-MB-00 antennas in a multi-GNSS approach can yield competitive results. Worse results obtained for two TWI7972 + GP NONE antennas may be proof of the lower similarity of their phase center characteristic between specimens. In Configuration D, on the other hand, antenna set #7 with u-blox ANN-MB-00 and TRM159900.00 NONE meets the adopted requirements and yields results that are comparable to those achieved using high-grade antennas. In general, the poorest results were obtained for Configuration E with nonhomogenous low-cost antennas.

5. Conclusions

The low-cost DF receivers and antennas have provided opportunities for a wide range of new applications in regions and fields where traditional GNSS equipment is beyond reasonable price. However, low-cost equipment has a serious drawback: the antenna radiation pattern is poorly defined, which causes positioning performance degradation. Motivated by the availability of PCC corrections for selected low-cost antennas, we analyzed the applicability of such antennas for precise surveying applications. With an ultra-short baseline scenario and relative positioning mode, we analyzed the antenna impact on ambiguity resolution and coordinate domains. With such an experimental design, we were able to isolate antenna-related errors from the atmospheric propagation ones.

Analyzing the number of recorded observations, SNR, and ambiguity resolution success ratio, it was found that meaningful discrepancies between antennas can be noticed. We found that low-cost antennas can record more observations than geodetic-grade ones, up to several percent in the case of Galileo signals. This is, however, related to their construction and the possibility of recording more signals from low-elevated satellites, also including reflected signals. In the case of GPS, however, the differences were negligible. When it comes to the ambiguity resolution domain, it was reported that

the best-performing results were obtained when the homogenous antennas were used in the baseline. For example, for the TRM105000.10 NONE surveying antenna pair, the ambiguity success rate reached 100%. For other cases where homogenous low-cost antennas were involved, the mean ambiguity success rates were only slightly lower, but the differences were not significant and usually did not exceed a few percent. Such outcomes proved the feasibility of high ambiguity resolution performance of phase data acquired with low-cost antennas.

More obvious differences were noticed in the case of SNR. Comparing results from low-cost and high-grade antennas, we found noticeable differences in SNR between the antennas. This is especially true for L2 and E5a frequencies. As expected, the highest SNR of GNSS signals was detected for the high-grade antennas.

Analyzing the results in the geometry domain, it was confirmed that the lowest discrepancies with respect to the benchmark parameters, such as height differences and distances, were obtained when a pair of homogenous surveying-grade antennas were used. What is worth highlighting is that there were cases when homogenous low-cost antennas were involved and also provided comparable performance. For precise distance and height difference determinations, a multi-GNSS solution with the same types of antennas, high-grade or low-cost ones, used at all network sites can be considered the best performing. Generally, we obtained the lowest distance and height difference residuals in such cases.

We also proved that precise height difference determination using GNSS technology is still challenging. The main reason for that is the fact that the vertical component of the GNSS position is typically characterized by an error 1.7 times higher than the horizontal coordinates, which is attributed to the geometry of GNSS satellites. However, as shown also, the receiver antenna PCV effect importantly influences the determination of the vertical component of the position. In our opinion, type-mean PCC models are not sufficient for precise height determinations. We assume that the use of individual PCC models, also for low-cost antennas, can provide an accuracy enhancement. This issue is worth further study.

Finally, the results exposed that low-cost antenna limitations have a meaningful impact on the performance of precise GNSS applications. Usually, the results obtained using low-cost antennas are characterized by higher deviations with respect to benchmark values than those obtained using surveying or geodetic ones. However, in certain configurations, like when using homogenous antennas in a relative positioning mode, the differences are not significant, and the results proved that low-cost sensors of this type could be successfully used in many engineering applications, especially those performed on short baselines.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13336140>.

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ORCID iDs

Karol Dawidowicz <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8837-700X>

Jacek Paziewski <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6033-2547>

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